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Crisis Management Strategies for School Leaders Affecting Academic Administration in Private Schools Under Nakhonratchasima Province Education Office

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Abstract

The purposes of this research were 1) to study the level of crisis management strategies for school leaders in private schools, 2) to study the level of academic administration in private schools, 3) to create forecasting equations for academic administration from crisis management strategies for private school leaders, and 4) to propose guidelines for developing strategies for crisis management for leaders of private schools. Population in the research study consisted of school administrators (school leaders) and teachers of private schools, 4,086 persons. The sample consisted of 351 persons, selected from simple random sampling, stratified random sampling, and proportional randomization. Statistics used for data analysis were mean, standard deviation and stepwise multiple regression analysis. The study results indicated that 1) crisis management strategies for school leaders in private schools were at a high level as a whole, namely, preparedness to facilitate a crisis that may happen and creating a crisis management plan had the highest mean while setting a structure of crisis communication had the lowest mean, 2) overall academic administration in private schools was at a high level, namely, internal quality assurance system and education standard had the highest mean while measurement, evaluation and the implementation of school record transfer had the lowest mean, 3) crisis management strategies had 3 aspects being able to predict academic administration in private schools, i.e. establishing a specific unit and a declarer, creating an effective stakeholder communication plan, and setting goals and objectives, with the statistical significance at 0.05 level, which could collaboratively predict academic administration in private schools under Nakhon Ratchasima Province Education Office by 51.40%, 4) guidelines for crisis management strategy development for school leaders of private schools are potential and external factor evaluation, i.e. 1) analysis of strength and weakness, 2) analysis of opportunity and feasibility for response, 3) consideration of obstacles and difficulties of external environment that may happy, 4) application of research findings – strategies that are appropriate and consistent with the determined objectives should be selected. As for creating an effective stakeholder communication plan and setting goals and objectives should be aware of internal and external situations that arise to have mutual understanding and to ensure the operations shall meet the goals, schemes, and run in the same direction.

Keywords: Administrative Strategy, Crisis, School Leaders, Academic Administration

1. Introduction

Crisis management is an organization's process and strategy-based approach for identifying and responding to a threat, an unanticipated event, or any negative disruption with the potential to harm people, organization, property, reputation and business profits. Most crises take place without any early warning. As a consequence, awareness of the importance and process of crisis management is important to organizational strategies, which should be developed to be strategic planning. Crisis management is divided into 3 types of crisis according to the degrees of organizational responsibility as victim cluster, accidental cluster, and preventable cluster. A case study of crisis management from Oishi Green Tea Company was foreign materials were found in green tea bottles, making Khun Tan Passakornatee, Chief Executive of the company had to solve that crisis by making a formal apology and pay a visit to customers who were affected in person, including providing medical expenses to all victims. Besides, he explained to public about the mistake that happened and confirmed the careful production process so as to build confidence among consumers (Preedee Nukulomprattana, 2020: 12).

Educational institution administrators play an important role as the leaders need to make a paradigm shift and develop strategies to manage transformational change in their organizations for success. Educational institution administrators must possess leadership and encourage subordinates to collaboratively work in an efficient manner, which can reduce and eliminate problems. Leadership plays a vital role in developing people in organizations and has an influence of the working of coworkers in a situation. A crisis of virus spread causing diseases had an impact on organizations. Employee morale and motivation are something that educational institution administrators need to take care of and access to build confidence among them and parents. Effectiveness of educational institutions comes from the way educational institutions are able to run the operations to achieve the set goals or objectives. Consideration is made to the ability in producing students with high learning achievement, students are developed to have positive attitude, students are able to solve problems with life skills and the 21st century skills according to the goals of education in a quality manner, including allocating resources, documents, media, technology equipment in an appropriate manner, having sufficient budgets and human resources, management and control to ensure the operations achieve efficiency and effectiveness and explicit practices (Rattana Leuangam, 2019: 3).

Private schools under Nakhon Ratchasima Province Education Office have major missions in promoting and supporting basic education management. There are 118 schools under Nakhon Ratchasima Province Education Office. They have a vision to develop education and 5 missions to promote education management, basic education services thoroughly. Education is determined in strategy 4 – the development of quality of life and policy 3 – to promote and support opportunity expansion and to establish the foundation of education to meet international standards. Policy is set to enable education to access people. All people must have equal opportunity to quality education. People have knowledge, virtue, and ethics, leading to preparedness to be consistent with the situation of disease spread that schools were unable to manage normal teaching and learning. Administrators needed to adjust the direction of education management to online teaching and learning to be compliant with daily life situation. It was a challenge for managing educational institutions to have efficiency and effectiveness for students in order to gain confidence from parents. Private educational institutions under Nakhon Ratchasima Province Education Office, Network 1-8, provide administration and education management in accordance with administrative areas. There are 118 schools affiliated to Nakhon Ratchasima Province Education Office (Private Education Promotion Group under Nakhon Ratchasima Province Education Office, 2021: 7).

From the process mentioned above, the researcher was interested in studying crisis management strategies for school leaders that affect academic administration in private schools under Nakhon Ratchasima Province Education to be used as a guideline for educational institution administrators to employ the study results to be information for managing educational institutions to achieve efficiency and effectiveness as much as possible, consistent with current situations and beneficial to operation planning, and to set policy for developing administrators and teachers that will affect quality development and education management to achieve the set goals and success in educational institution management accordingly.

2. Research Objectives

- 1) To study the level of crisis management strategies for school leaders in private schools under Nakhon Ratchasima Province Education Office.
- 2) To study the level of academic administration in private schools under Nakhon Ratchasima Province Education Office.
- 3) To create forecasting equations for academic administration from crisis management strategies for private school leaders under Nakhon Ratchasima Province Education Office.
- 4) To propose guidelines for developing strategies for crisis management for leaders of private schools under Nakhon Ratchasima Province Education Office.

3. Research methodology

This research aimed to study crisis management strategies for educational institution administrators that affect academic administration in private schools under Nakhon Ratchasima Province Education Office. The study was conducted in the form of survey research. Data were collected from a questionnaire.

3.1. The scope of population

1.1 Population in the study consisted of school administrators and teachers in 118 private schools under Nakhon Ratchasima Province Education Office, from the academic year 2022, a total of 4,086 persons.

1.2 The sample – the number and size of the sample were calculated using G* Power (Nipitpon Sanitleua, Watchareeporn Sadphet, and Yada Napa-arak, 2019). The sample of 351 persons consisted of school administrators and teachers, selected by simple random sampling, stratified random sampling, and proportional randomization) according to the size of schools.

3.2. The scope of content

The purpose of the study is to investigate crisis management strategies for school leaders in private schools under Nakhon Ratchasima Province Education Office in 4 aspects consisting of 1) setting goals and objectives, 2) selecting strategies in response to a crisis, 3) creating an effective stakeholder communication plan, and 4) establishing a specific unit and a declarer, and to investigate academic administration in private schools under Nakhon Ratchasima Province Education Office in 7 aspects comprising 1) curriculum development in educational institutions, 2) learning process development, 3) measurement, evaluation, and the implementation of school record transfer, 4) research for education quality development in educational institutions, 5) educational supervision, 6) the development of internal quality assurance system and educational standard, 7) the development and use of technology and teaching innovation for education.

3.3. Instruments in the study

Part 1: A questionnaire about individual status of respondents.

Part 2: A questionnaire about crisis management strategies for school leaders in private schools under Nakhon Ratchasima Province Education Office in 4 aspects consisting of 1) setting goals and objectives, 2) selecting strategies in response to a crisis, 3) creating an effective stakeholder communication plan, 4) establishing a specific unit and a declarer. The questionnaire consists of 5-point Likert scale survey questions, ranging from highest, high, moderate, low, and lowest.

Part 3: A questionnaire about academic administration in private schools under Nakhon Ratchasima Province Education Office in 7 aspects, namely, 1) curriculum development in educational institutions, 2) learning process development, 3) measurement, evaluation, and the implementation of school record transfer, 4) research for education quality development in educational institutions, 5) educational supervision, 6) the development of internal quality assurance system and educational standard, 7) the development and use of technology and teaching

innovation for education. The questionnaire consists of 5-point Likert scale survey questions, ranging from highest, high, moderate, low, and lowest.

Part 4: Opinions and suggestions.

The 2nd research instrument is an interview form about guidelines for developing crisis management strategies for school leaders affecting academic administration in private schools under Nakhon Ratchasima Province Education Office in 4 aspects consisting of 1) setting goals and objectives, 2) selecting strategies in response to a crisis, 3) creating an effective stakeholder communication plan, 4) establishing a specific unit and a declarer. There are 4 items of open-ended questions and questions about academic administration in private schools under Nakhon Ratchasima Province Education Office in 7 aspects consisting of 1) curriculum development in educational institutions, 2) learning process development, 3) measurement, evaluation, and the implementation of school record transfer, 4) research for education quality development in educational institutions, 5) educational supervision, 6) the development of internal quality assurance system and educational standard, 7) the development and use of technology and teaching innovation for education. There are 7 items of open-ended questions and there are 11 items for interviewing school leaders and suggestions from school leaders.

3.4. Making and testing research instruments

1. Study how to make a questionnaire for data collection from documents and textbooks related to crisis management and academic administration in educational institutions.
2. Study relevant concepts, theories and research documents by considering details to ensure they cover the determined research objective.
3. Make a questionnaire that covers the research objective for collecting data from the sample and making an analysis.
4. The questionnaire was presented to the advisor to examine accuracy and appropriateness for making improvement.
5. The created questionnaire was presented to 5 experts in educational institution management to test content validity. The item-objective congruence index (IOC) was set at 0.50 or greater. It was found that IOC of all questions was 1.00.
6. The tested questionnaire was measured discrimination power and reliability using Pearson's correlation coefficient and Cronbach's alpha coefficient respectively. The questionnaire was pretested with 30 people who are not the research sample. Internal consistency was measured. The reliability of the questionnaire was 0.98.

3.5. Data analysis

1. Analyze status of respondents using frequency and percentage.
2. Analyze crisis management strategies for school leaders in private schools under Nakhon Ratchasima Province Education Office by calculating mean and standard deviation and interpreting the meaning of score levels based on Best's scoring criteria (Best, 1977:174).
3. Analyze academic administration in private schools under Nakhon Ratchasima Province Education Office by calculating mean and standard deviation and interpreting the meaning of score levels based on Best scoring criteria (Best, 1977:174).
4. The analysis of crisis management strategies for school leaders affecting academic administration in private schools under Nakhon Ratchasima Province Education Office was conducted using multiple regression analysis and stepwise multiple regression analysis.

3.6. Statistics for data analysis

Statistics used for data processing and analysis are

1. basic statistics, i.e. percentage, mean, and standard deviation.
2. statistics used to measure the quality of research instruments, i.e. IOC (Index of item objective congruence), Cronbach's Alpha to measure reliability.

3. statistics for testing, i.e. stepwise multiple regression analysis.

4. Research results

Details of the analysis results of crisis management for school leaders in private schools under Nakhon Ratchasima Province Education Office are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Mean, standard deviation, and crisis management for school leaders in private schools under Nakhon Ratchasima Province Education Office overall and in each aspect.

Aspect	Crisis management for school leaders in private schools under Nakhon Ratchasima Province Education Office	Levels of crisis management			
		$\bar{X}$	SD	Interpret	Rank
1.	Setting goals and objectives	3.75	.74	High	3
2.	Selecting strategies in response to a crisis	3.73	.85	High	4
3.	Creating an effective stakeholder communication plan	3.82	.76	High	2
4.	Establishing a specific unit and a declarer	3.85	.81	High	1
Total		3.79	.70	High	

From Table 1, it was found that overall crisis management for school leaders in private schools under Nakhon Ratchasima Province Education Office was at a high level ($\bar{X} = 3.79$, $SD = 0.81$). When each aspect was considered, it was found that all aspects were at a high level as arranged from the highest mean to the lowest mean, namely, establishing a specific unit and a declarer = 0.81, creating an effective stakeholder communication plan ($\bar{X} = 3.82$, $SD = 0.76$), setting goals and objectives ($\bar{X} = 3.75$, $SD = 0.74$), and selecting strategies in response to a crisis ($\bar{X} = 3.73$, $SD = 0.74$).

Details of the analysis results of academic administration in private schools under Nakhon Ratchasima Province Education Office are shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Mean, standard deviation, and academic administration in private schools under Nakhon Ratchasima Province Education Office overall and in each aspect (Y_{tot}).

No.	Academic administration in private schools under Nakhon Ratchasima Province Education Office	Levels of academic administration			
		$\bar{X}$	SD	Interpret	Rank
1.	Curriculum development in educational institutions	3.83	.89	High	5
2.	Learning process development	3.82	.78	High	6
3.	Measurement, evaluation, and the implementation of school record transfer	3.62	.96	High	7
4.	Research for education quality development in educational institutions	3.90	.89	High	4
5.	Educational supervision	3.93	.71	High	3
6.	The development of internal quality assurance system and educational standard	4.03	.79	High	1
7.	The development and use of technology and teaching innovation for education	4.02	.75	High	2
Total		3.88	.58	High	

From Table 4.7, it was found that overall academic administration in private schools under Nakhon Ratchasima Province Education Office was at a high level ($\bar{X} = 3.77$, $SD = 0.66$). When each aspect was considered, it was found that all aspects were at a high level as arranged from the highest mean to the lowest mean, namely, the development of internal quality assurance system and educational standard ($\bar{X} = 4.07$, $SD = 1.03$), the

development and use of technology and teaching innovation for education ($\bar{X} = 4.02$, $SD = 0.75$), educational supervision ($\bar{X} = 3.93$, $SD = 0.71$), research for education quality development in educational institutions ($\bar{X} = 3.90$, $SD = 0.89$), curriculum development in educational institutions ($\bar{X} = 3.83$, $SD = 0.89$), learning process development ($\bar{X} = 3.82$, $SD = 0.78$), and measurement, evaluation, and the implementation of school record transfer ($\bar{X} = 3.62$, $SD = 0.96$).

Table 3: Tolerance value and variance inflation factor (VIF) value.

Variables	Tolerance	VIF
1. Setting goals and objectives	0.381	2.625
2. Selecting strategies in response to a crisis	0.308	3.248
3. Creating an effective stakeholder communication plan	0.281	3.561
4. Establishing a specific unit and a declarer	0.401	2.494

From Table 3, multicollinearity check was performed to test whether or not independent variables are correlated as it affects regression analysis by enabling analysis results to have errors. Tolerance value should be greater than 0.1 and variance inflation factor (VIF) value should be lower than 10 which will not cause a problem that variables are correlated (Multicollinearity). The test according to Table 2 found that tolerance value ranged from 0.281 to 0.401, greater than 0.1, and VIF value ranged from 2.494 to 3.561, not greater than 10. Therefore, there was no problems that variables were correlated (Multicollinearity).

Table 4: Crisis management variables affecting academic administration in private schools under Nakhon Ratchasima Province Education Office as a whole (Y_{tot}).

Predictor variables according to the sequence of the equation	Unstandardized		standardized	t	Sig
	Coefficients	Std. Error	Coefficients		
	$\hat{\beta}$		Beta		
Constant value	1.646	.124		13.318	.000
Establishing a specific unit and declarer (X_4)	.290	.042	.403	6.843	.000
Creating an effective stakeholder communication plan (X_3)	.209	.050	.273	4.201	.000
Setting goals and objectives (X_1)	.087	.042	.110	2.056	.041

*Statistical significance level of .05.

According to Table 3, it was found that among 4 aspects of crisis management strategies affecting academic administration in private schools under Nakhon Ratchasima Province Education Office, there were 3 aspects that could predict academic administration in private schools under Nakhon Ratchasima Province Education Office, namely, establishing a specific unit and declarer (X_4), creating an effective stakeholder communication plan (X_3), and setting goals and objectives (X_1), with the statistical significance level of 0.05.

These 3 aspects could cooperatively predict academic administration in private schools under Nakhon Ratchasima Province Education Office by 51.40%.

The equation of multiple regression analysis can be written in the form of raw score as follow:

$$\hat{Y}_{tot} = 1.646 + 0.290(X_4) + 0.209(X_3) + 0.087(X_1)$$

The predictor equation can be written in the form of standard score as follow:

$$\hat{Z} Y_{tot} = 0.403(X_4) + 0.273(X_3) + 0.110(X_1)$$

5. Discussion

1. Overall crisis management for school leaders in private schools under Nakhon Ratchasima Province Education Office was at a high level. It is possible that during the past 3 years there was a severe communicable disease. In this regard, schools hold a meeting with communities and parents for crisis management by establishing a specific unit and declarer as the center in coordinating between schools and communities, setting goals and objectives, creating an effective stakeholder communication plan, and selecting strategies in response to a crisis to cope with the crisis and create a mechanism to avoid the crisis. In case being unable to avoid the crisis, they knew how to control the situation to ensure the least damage instead of letting the situation continue without knowing how to handle it or learn how to bring the organization to a normal situation as soon as possible. This is consistent with a research study of AbdElaal, AbdElaal AbdAllah; Al Shobaki, Mazen J.; Abu-Naser, Samy S.; El Talla, Suliman A. (2022) on effects of strategic planning on crisis management in a ceramic company in Egypt. The study aimed to identify effects of strategic planning on crisis management in a ceramic company in Egypt. Descriptive analysis was used through a questionnaire. The study results revealed that chief executives agreed with all dimensions of strategic planning variables. It was found that every procedure of the crisis was apparently applied to the ceramic company studied. The study results also indicated the existence of significant effects and statistical significance of the dimensions of strategic planning variables on strategy variables. The most important suggestions of crisis management and crisis management procedures from the points of view of chief executives were the necessity that every level in the organization must participate in the process of strategic planning, the development of basic procedure for crisis management planning, the necessity of establishing a work unit for crisis management, organizational structure, and the use of competent employees. A study conducted by George Spais & Pallab Paulb (2021) on a crisis management model for marketing education: reflections on marketing education system's transformation in view of Covid-19 crisis. The primary objective of the study is to apply a crisis management model to marketing education in distress due to the Covid-19 pandemic. A strategic approach to managing crisis was used, first introduced by Burnett, to provide a conceptual framework for managing teaching turmoil and triumphs during this pandemic. An in-depth discussion of literature was conducted, a critical realist's perspective was adopted, current examples of universities' best practices and decisions for each of the three phases of crisis management (identification, confrontation, and reconfiguration) were provided for successful recovery during these trying times. As the gap between theory and practice remains a critical concern among scholars, the article and proposed framework shall present a unique opportunity to explore and study how unexpected changes occur in higher education, and their remedies. However, based on the need to reflect on the nature of current marketing education through crisis management, the implications of the framework were identified and valuable suggestions were offered for future research.

2. Overall academic administration in private schools under Nakhon Ratchasima Province Education Office was at a high level. It is possible that schools have academic administration consistent with Ministry of Education and school policies. Development is made to internal quality assurance system and education standard, development and the use of technology and teaching innovation for education, educational supervision, curriculum development in educational institutions, research for education quality development in educational institutions, and learning process development. This is consistent with the concept of the Office of Basic Education Commission (2017:33). Previously, academic administration in educational institutions was separated from management. The Ministry assigned each department to oversee educational institutions under their affiliation to carry out the operations according to the policies determined; for example, Department of General Education oversees and takes responsible for secondary education, Office of National Education Commission oversees primary education, making the academic operations in educational institutions lack of unity as it depends on each department shall assign educational institutions under their affiliation to carry out. Ministry of Education views that it does not cover the provisions in the National Education Act B.E. 2542 (1999) and the Amendment B.E. 2545 (2002) in which emphasis is placed on curriculum reform and learning based on human development according to the education principles that aim to develop Thai people to become a perfect human being as prescribed in the Section 22-30, and the use of technology for education in Section 47. In this regard, a scope of practice guideline for academic administration is prepared to encourage all basic educational institutions to implement. A research study conducted by Supaporn Piladram (2019) on effectiveness of academic administration in schools under Nakhon Ratchasima Provincial Administrative Organization found that 1) the effectiveness of

academic administration in schools under Nakhon Ratchasima Provincial Administrative Organization was overall at a high level according to the opinions of educational institution administrators and teachers in schools under Nakhon Ratchasima Provincial Administrative Organization, consistent with a research study conducted by Siwaporn Lahanpetch (2019) on the effectiveness of academic administration in small size schools according to the opinions of teachers under Surat Thani Primary Educational Service Area Office 2. The study results found that 1) the mean effectiveness of academic administration in small size schools according to the opinions of teachers under Surat Thani Primary Educational Service Area Office 2 overall and in each aspect was at a high level.

3. The analysis results of regression coefficient of crisis management strategies affecting academic administration in private schools under Nakhon Ratchasima Province Education Office found there were 4 aspects of crisis management strategies affecting academic administration in private schools under Nakhon Ratchasima Province Education Office and only 3 aspects could cooperatively predict academic administration in private schools under Nakhon Ratchasima Province Education Office by 51.40%, i.e. establishing a specific unit and declarer (X_4), creating an effective stakeholder communication plan (X_3), and setting goals and objectives (X_1), with the statistical significance level of 0.05. It is possible that crisis management is something new to school administrators and teachers. If school administrators and teachers do not have expertise in being a declarer and using communication technology with stakeholders under such crisis, the operations are unable to reach the set goals and objectives. Preedee Nukulomprattana (2020) said that establishing a specific unit and an announcer or declarer of the organization is establishing a work team associated with how to cope with a crisis to become the center of operations and coordination with stakeholders. A declarer in a crisis must possess the following qualifications: 1. Work team must have full authority for crisis management since a crisis cannot wait. Full authority given shall support agility in problem solving. 2. A declarer must have expertise and proficiency in communication and sincere image. 3. Work team must have emotional stability to work under huge pressure with various situations. Work team must have fact and understand the situation they are confronting correctly and clearly. A research study conducted by Atiporn Nilkham, Saowanee Sikkabandit and Khwanying Sriprasertpap (2022) on a model of school administration in Coronavirus disease 2019 crisis for schools under the supervision of Bangkok Metropolitan Administration found that 1) overall school administration in Coronavirus disease 2019 crisis was at a high level. Prevention and reduction of effects were the most widely practiced, followed by disaster preparedness, crisis management, and post-crisis management that were practiced at a high level, 2) Confirmatory factor analysis results of school administration in Coronavirus disease 2019 crisis included 4 factors. The factor with the highest factor loading was prevention and reduction of effects, followed by disaster preparedness, crisis management, and post-crisis management, 3) Evaluation results of appropriateness, feasibility, accuracy and application were at the highest level as a whole. There were 4 factors in school administration in Coronavirus disease 2019 crisis. All factor loadings were statistically significant at 0.05. The factor with the highest factor loading was prevention and reduction of effect, factor loading was 0.90, followed by disaster preparedness, crisis management, and post-crisis management which factor loadings were 0.89, 0.87, and 0.82 respectively.

6. Qualitative data analysis

According to qualitative data, guidelines for developing crisis management strategies for school leaders in private schools under Nakhon Ratchasima Province Education Office are as follow:

1. Most school leaders gave opinions and agreed that strategic plans and objectives of crisis management should be determined. Internal and external school problems must be studied. Selecting strategies in response to problems must be carefully analyzed, proactive and reactive analysis, changing or improving in accordance with the framework and resources available. Potential and external factors should be evaluated, i.e. 1) strength and weakness, 2) opportunity and feasibility in response, 3) obstacles and difficulties of external environment that may happen, 4) selecting strategies appropriate to and consistent with the determined objectives. Creating an effective stakeholder communication plan and setting up goals and objectives must enable stakeholders to be aware of internal and external situations that occur to make mutual understanding and to ensure the operations shall meet the set goals, model, and go in the same direction. Schools should give an opportunity to students, local communities, and parents to participate in the management of online teaching and learning. Emphasis is placed on combining knowledge with innovation, appointing a crisis management committee from external experts. A lie

and prediction are not allowed in communication. Stories must be told straightforwardly and honestly. If mistakes are made by schools, an apology should be made. With regard to establishing a specific unit and declarer, a school committee should be appointed by recruiting employees in the organization who have knowledge in a certain crisis and ability to solve unexpected problems. A declarer must have good communication skills and reliable personality as he/she needs to play the role of mediator when declaring messages, have belief, thinking model and demands to do something including listening to information from various channels to support planning and setting the goals for communication and partners in communication for seeking an alliance to support communication and build credibility in coping with and manage a certain crisis.

2. With regard to academic administration, most school leaders viewed that teaching and learning curriculum should be various and teaching models should be adjusted to both offline and online. Demands of parents and local communities should be studied. Core curriculum and other information should be analyzed. The context of arising crisis should be studied to bring the information to develop the curriculum to be consistent with the context of schools and demands of parents, local communities, and current situations. Additional courses should be provided in accordance with aptitude/interest. A curriculum must be evaluated from relevant persons before being used. Learning process should be adjusted to have flexibility and respond to learners with a variety of development adhering to the guidelines of learning management process and the development of learners' quality introduced by Ministry of Education, i.e. 1. Be able to read and write fluently. 2. Be fluent in math. 3. Have basic thinking skills and higher order thinking skills. 4. Have life skills. 5. Have creative communication skills by age and foreign language skills. 6. Seek knowledge on one's own and seek knowledge for problem solving. 7. Use technology for learning. 8. Be high-minded and long for knowledge. 9. Have sufficient living, be committed to education and the development of teachers and all employees to have knowledge and ability in using various technology media. Professional learning community (PLC) is used to enhance learning management. Teachers' learning management is inspected and monitored continuously. Measurement, evaluation, and the implementation of school record transfer, authentic assessment, and research are information promoting and supporting the quality of education to be useful for schools' education management. Problems and demands in learning development of learners must be analyzed. Activity management is planned. Problem solving is carried out. Information is collected and problem solving outcomes are concluded, consistent with crisis management strategies of educational institutions. Supervision is the process of improving and developing the quality of education based on cooperation between supervisors and supervisees according to democratic practice. Emphasis is placed on giving assistance and suggestion while supervisees accept for the benefit of efficiency of education management so as to follow up teaching process to meet the set goals and strategies. The development of quality assurance system should allow every party to participate in the process, both inside and outside educational institutions. Planning-implementation-inspection are conducted. The outcomes obtained shall be used to improve. Emphasis is placed on the quality of learners in accordance with the 2018 ministerial regulation on the quality assurance of education of Office of the Private Education Commission. The development of technology and innovation is the process that supports all systems in terms of management system, learning management, sufficient provision including the development of education management using instruments, equipment, media to manage education to be modern, consistent with the context of a crisis that arises. Teachers and all employees have to be developed to have knowledge and ability to use technology media and teaching innovation.

7. Conclusion/suggestions

7.1. Suggestions from the research results

1.1. Setting goals and objectives – the point with the lowest mean is setting up the structure of crisis communication. Therefore, school leaders should hold a meeting to determine the setting up of the structure of crisis communication by clearly establishing a work unit for crisis management in terms of who will take responsibility to ensure the crisis management is more efficient.

1.2 Selecting strategies in response to a crisis – the point with the lowest mean in the organization has preparedness to cope with and solve problems caused by a crisis. School leaders should select strategies appropriate to arising situations. In case a crisis is caused by schools, school leaders should select the apology strategy. The school

makes an apology and is willing to provide assistance and remedy in all cases. If a crisis is not caused by schools, school leaders should select the denial strategy. The school must be certain that the arising crisis is not associated with the school and the school needs to inform the public clearly and straightforwardly.

1.3 Creating an effective stakeholder communication plan – the point with the lowest mean is organizations communicate with people in the organizations and all stakeholders. Thus, school leaders and teachers should make plan to communicate with communities and students' parents about an arising crisis and work cooperatively to solve the problem to ensure crisis management is efficient.

1.4 Establishing a specific unit and declarer – the point with the lowest mean is establishing an operations center including coordinating with internal and external work units, Schools should establish an operations center including coordinating with internal and external work units to ensure crisis management is efficient.

1.5 Curriculum development in educational institutions – the point with the lowest mean is educational institutions improve the curriculum through the process of analyzing documents, problems, community demands, internal and external environment. Schools should give an opportunity to people outside like communities to participate in curriculum development to analyze documents, solve problems, consistent with community demands and to manage internal and external environment.

1.6 Learning process development – the point with the lowest mean is educational institutions promote teachers to make a student-centered learning management plan. Schools should promote teachers to make a student-centered learning management plan. Teacher should be allowed to attend a training course on student-centered teaching and learning with external agencies so that teachers can bring the knowledge obtained to develop a learning management plan. Measurement, evaluation and the implementation of school record transfer – the point with the lowest mean is educational institutions have the transfer system of school records, knowledge, skills, and experiences from other educational institutions when new students move in. Schools should have the transfer system of school records, knowledge, skills, and experiences from other educational institutions when new students move in for convenience and quickness in teaching and learning management.

1.7 Research for the development of education quality in educational institutions – the point with the lowest mean is educational institutions implement research in a systematic manner. Schools should implement research systematically by promoting teachers to conduct research according to leaning strands for developing academic quality. Research results can be used to improve teachers' teaching and learning management to gain more efficiency.

1.8 Educational supervision – the point with the lowest mean is educational institutions explicitly set the goals and objectives of the supervision. Schools should explicitly set the goals and objectives of the supervision. The outcomes from the educational supervision can be used to improve teaching and learning, support academic supervision and teaching and learning in various models which will be suitable for schools.

1.9 The development of internal quality assurance system and education standard – the point with the lowest mean is educational institutions manage an organizational structure to facilitate the evaluation from original affiliation and the Office for National Education Standards and Quality Assessment (Public Organization). Schools should manage the organizational structure to facilitate evaluation from original affiliation and the Office for National Education Standards and Quality Assessment (Public Organization) by assigning teachers of each learning strand to monitor, inspect, and evaluate internal quality to make continuous improvement and development and to make a plan to develop education quality of schools regularly.

1.10 Development and the use of technology and teaching innovation for education – the point with the lowest mean is educational institutions promote teachers to develop media, innovation and technology for education. Schools should promote teachers to develop media, innovation and technology for education by providing a training course and knowledge about the development and the use of technology and teaching innovation for

education so that they are able to improve and develop instructional media to be modern and keep pace with current technology.

7.2. Suggestions for future studies

2.1 A study should be conducted on a guideline for developing leadership appropriate to a crisis in private schools under Nakhon Ratchasima Province Education Office so that study results can be used for preparedness of how to cope with a crisis that may happen in the future.

2.2 A study should be conducted on factors affecting efficiency of the development of media and technology for education of small size schools under Nakhon Ratchasima Province Education Office. The information obtained can be used as a guideline for developing media and technology for education in small size schools.

2.3 A study should be conducted on models for developing teachers' learning process in private schools under Nakhon Ratchasima Province Education Office. The information obtained can be used as a guideline for developing teachers' learning process.

2.4 A study should be conducted on crisis management strategies for educational institution administrators by using qualitative data and focus group so as to obtain in-depth information.

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